

A Sociological Analysis of Intersectionality between the Creation of a Creative Writer and the Role of Education

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Abstract

Despite the enormous intellectual effort taken to liberate art and literature from the discourse surrounded by the religious creeds, the meaning of the production of literature and the writer is concealed. The current state of concealment is social, entangled with various modalities of power structures which largely emanate from various domains of literary production. Over the last few decades, sociologists have struggled to unravel the obscured ideas entangled with literary production that assign significance to the role of education in the production of literature and writers. In the Sri Lankan context, sociology of literature as an area of study and the role of education has been overlooked. This article deals with the learning experience of the participants and their struggle to apply the concepts and techniques based on the training workshops conducted by the Department of Cultural affairs in Sri Lanka to train amateur writers. Qualitative method was used to gather data in which 146 evaluation reports on several sessions by 35 participants and 5 case studies were conducted. Findings were analyzed using the thematic approach while data gathered from the evaluation reports were quantified. Based on Bourdieu's concept of *habitus*, this article argues that participants' struggle in the learning process can be understood as historically constituted structuring process.

Keywords: Sociology of literature, education, writer and writing, habitus, post-coloniality

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Introduction

Story telling is a vital part of articulating one's experiences which goes back to the origins of humans' story. An individual's effort to express a personal experience developed to the complex level of fabricating a story is known as 'fiction' today. This development is solely an expansion of our cognitive skills. In the process of nurturing the religious mind throughout its human history, much of the mystic attitudes and values invested to define the process of creative writing and the writer, centers around 'the writer' as a unique individual possessing a supreme set of mysterious skills.

The article aims to explore the experience of learning in the context of the construction of a creative writer and its sociological significance. I use the word creative writing to signify the broad range of literary practices including writing novels or fictions, short stories and poetry. Based on the theoretical perspective of Bourdieu (2007) and his idea of 'habitus' in the context of sociology of art and education, the article explores how participants perceive creative writing as a social production and hence the creator is a product of the social process (Becker, 2008) in which participants demonstrate their experiences in the journey of learning to be a creative writer. In conventional understanding, the skills for artistic productions including creative writing have been considered as indigenous to the genius of the writer and making their literary work unique (Zolberg, 1990).

However, the idea of 'unique' and 'genius' of an artist, glorifies the skills and techniques which are invested in the production of art, obscure its meaning by assigning metaphysical qualities such as luck, and God given talent or a skill inherited from the previous generation. This has been the idea propagated in school curricula on art and literature. Hindrance of the idea of art as a social production is explicitly demonstrated in schools and university curriculums in literature. For example, the literary devices in a novel, poetry or in a short story which are illustrated in art appreciation courses or discussions will be used in a similar fashion in writer training workshops as well.

This current assumption regarding the artistic production and the creation of an artist or writer has been challenged by sociologists from different perspectives. In this context, Zolberg (1990) foregrounds an important question on this matter. She asks whether an artist is born or produced? In her book, *Constructing the Sociology of Arts*, Zolberg examines the idea of creation an artist. Her attempts to understand the process of the genesis of art from sociological Perspective. It focuses on the ranges of factors that contribute to the development of artistic figure. In her analysis, education is only an element. Bourdieu (1980) explored the intersectionality between art and artistic taste in relation to the education and class. He explicitly argues education and class position of people determines their taste and appreciation of art. However, very few studies have explored the learning experience of a person on his or her way to be an artist or a writer. Particularly in Sri Lankan context, no study has attempted to understand neither the people perception of art or art practices in a sociological perspective nor the learning experience as the transformative character of their

journey. It is in this context this article attempts to explore the journey of the learning process of a group of people who are undergoing the training process of creative writing programme with the aim to be a novelist, short story writer or a poet. In the context where not only sociology of arts as a distinctive discipline was not developed, but also misinterpreted, this article provides useful analytical and interpretive grounds to understand the production aspect of literary figure through sociological perspective.

The study is based on the learning experiences of the group of adult participants who attended a series of training programmes on creative writing. The workshops were organized by the Department of Cultural affairs in Sri Lanka, with the intention of transforming the selected amateur creative writers to experienced professional writers. The programme was executed in four phases with three months' intervals over a period of year. The training sessions were based around six main themes, which aimed at holistically improving creative writing. Themes included (a) identification of plot and its development, (b) character building, (c) event building, (d) developing a narrative arc, (e) the techniques and the role of observation in overall creative process, and (f) the use of language. Each of these themes were centered around specifically designed activities for groups and individuals. More importantly, the activities were specifically designed to teach them how the above-mentioned literary devices are constructed in order to create a novel, a short story or a poem, against the conventional methods of teaching which teach them how to appreciate or critique a character in a novel or short story, its plot development, and event development, the use of imagination or the use of language. In these workshops, they were taught how to construct the above literary devices in meaningful manner.

Ideologically, the workshop is positioned against the traditional myth which sought the creation of an *artist* or *writer* as a result of the divine grace or skills received from unknown medium. In contrast, the programme is contextualized on the idea that '*a writer is a product of social process and can be developed or produced by instilling certain sets of skills and techniques in them*'. Education has been considered as one aspect of the social process. Based on Pierre Bourdieu's theoretical claim that taste or capacity to appreciate artistic expressions is a cultural disposition, a *habitus* determined by the class and education along with other social factors, the article attempts to examine the interrelationship between the person and the role of education in constructing a literary figure.

Bourdieu's (2007) idea of *habitus* is used to understand how existing dispositional knowledge and beliefs on creation of art, an artist in Sri Lankan context constraints their development. To understand the above, this article is contextualized in a broader socio-economic and political context in relation to the art education in the country in which I argue that participants' struggle to comprehend the content delivered during the training sessions—use of literary devices from the perspective of creative process – is influenced by the pre-existing ideological stances cultivated by the education process. Their inability to unlearn the pre-existing ideologies on literary practices and re-learn it constructively is a result of the structuring process of education thorough out its history or in other words the *habitus*.

Research problem and the methodology

How do adults experience the role of education in developing a creative writer?

This research question aims to explore the participants' perception on the intersectionality between art and education through the experience of immersive learning process they underwent in the previously mentioned creative writing workshop. Ontologically, the research problem is situated on the assumption that an artist or a creative writer requires specific skills to produce a piece of art and is rare and laborious. However, in lay perceptions, obtaining such skills is considered as an arduous task, and is often mystified. Epistemologically, the study is situated in the scope of sociology of arts, which claims that production of both arts and artist is a social process. Based on the learning experience of the participants who attended the above-mentioned programme, this study attempted to understand the role of education in developing a creative writer and their perception of art. Moreover, the study also attempted to explore the participants' struggle in imparting new knowledge during the learning process. In the discussion, it also aimed to understand how their view of arts has been changed over the period of training.

The study employed a qualitative research approach to explore the above research problem. Accordingly, data were mainly collected using interviews and documents in which 10 respondents enunciated their learning experiences and transformative aspect of their attitudes on creative writing. In addition, I looked at the evaluation reports of participants in two training sessions. The comments emerged during the discussions were taken into the consideration. Accordingly, comments raised in 12 discussion sessions were taken into consideration. Moreover, evaluation reports of selected 35 participants in the two training sessions which consist of 146 evaluation documents on several sessions were also analyzed. In the research process, author employed emic and etic approaches to explore the subject matter, since the author as one architect of the above programme and as a resource person in the workshop. Accordingly, the development of their ideas in creative writing was examined through data gathered in three main sources. Qualitative data were analyzed using the thematic approach. The themes emerged from the interviews, evaluation reports and from the discussions were treated equally and looked at holistically.

Intersection between art, education and class

The sociological perspective on art has taken at least two main paths in its initial theoretical development. Initially institutions including Chicago School has taken the positivistic approach in defining art and art practices. These definitions of art and art practices have been viewed as a social process or social production than the artistic works as an outcome of the skills received from mysterious entities or inherited from unknown faculties (Becker, 2008). In his work *Art World*, Becker (2008) looks at our engagement with art and its outcome as a result of the social division of labor. While giving a significant attention to the economic aspect of art in its total production, Becker specifically argues how particular

forms of knowledge and skills are interwoven together to produce art work which he elaborates under the concept of 'cooperate link' and (Becker, 2008:24) Becker not only looks at the multiple contributors who contribute their skills but also a wide range of institutional arrangement including educational system that come in to play in the Art World.

Literature was not excluded from the sociological analysis of arts. In 1971, Escarpit writes on sociology of literature exploring its tri-part relationship between the text, author and the audience. In their analysis, sociologists' earliest battle was to establish the true meaning of sociological engagement in literature by liberating the word sociology from the misrepresentation in literature. As Griswold (1993: 455) noted, sociology of literature is like an amoeba, as it lacks a concrete structure perhaps because of the way the literary writers use it loosely. In popular discussions, it is often seen that phrases such as 'the sociological base of the text', 'sociologically reading' ... etc. are commonly used. In these phrases, the implication of the word 'sociological' has nothing to do with the subject sociology other than mere representation of society in it. Perhaps, this could be the result of Marxist approach over the text influenced by the writings of Raymond Williams (1971) and Terry Eagleton (1988). According to English, the word sociology in literature is used in general sense by "literary scholars in sub-fields such as post-colonial studies, queer theories and so forth" (English, 2010; vii).

As McKenzie rightly pointed out, sociologists' task is not the text, but the sociology of the text (McKenzie quoted in English, 2010). From the outset, sociologists like Escarpit (1971), Ibsch, Schram and Steen (1989), Radways (1984), engaged in a battle of establishing the field by extending its boundaries conceptually, theoretically and methodologically, though Lowenthal is exceptional because he vehemently refused searching and interpreting ideologies from the text. He did not use literary text as fact finding sources about social institutions and organizations (Lowenthal & Weeks, 1987). Unfortunately, these thematic debates demonstrate that neither the sociology of arts nor the sociology of literature has been established as a field of study in order to explore it in real sociological sense in the Sri Lankan context.

Writing about new tendencies of sociology of literature, English (2010) point out five stages of development which starts from text to the institutional aspects like education and to the reader. Intersectionality between education and literature is one such development. Works by Hunter (1988), Watkins (1989), Viswanathan (1989) are some notable examples that discuss the role of education in arts. These studies suggest literature has intricate relationship with education which shape and construct the production as well as the directions of literature through its educational practices ranging from teaching to syllabus and educators to beneficiaries.

Davies highlights how "separation of literature from other forms of written text were closely connected to the history and ideology of education" which concealed the real class struggle under the fictional construction of national unity (Davies quoted in Wolff, 1993: 14).

The relationship between art, education and class is one of the salient themes which has been widely discussed by Bourdieu (Davies quoted in Wolff, 1993). In his work *Aristocracy of culture* (1980) Bourdieu highlights the co-relationship between taste, art education and class. Driven by sophisticated statistical analysis, Bourdieu argues that the higher the educational achievements are, the greater the opportunity to acquire good taste or associate with high art. The less the educational achievement are the less the opportunity of being equipped with appreciation for art is going to be (Bourdieu, 1980). As he discussed, not only that less educated people demonstrated limited knowledge of recognizing a serious musical composer, but also correspond with the types of radio station that they listen to (*ibid*). Their level of taste or appropriation of the genre of music or preferences on radio station is determined by the level of education. As Bourdieu (1980) suggests, the level of education correlates with class as the position of class plays a decisive role in determining access to education. In his work *Aristocracy of culture*, Bourdieu analyzed the above facts on 20 plus occupational categories across three class positions: Laborers, middle level positions and upper-level positions. This can be further illustrated in his work on museum visit (Dicks, 2016).

By situating in the previously mentioned broader framework, this research attempts to fill useful gaps in addressing one of the important sociological questions in sociology of literature. By contributing to establish the sociology of literature as a distinct area of study, this paper explored how an educational program crafted on the ideology that the ‘writer can be produced’, is effective and how participants’ learning experience can be understood sociologically.

Bourdieu's (2007) idea of *habitus* provides an important theoretical framework to understand the learning experiences of the participants. Bourdieu's postulation of *habitus* is multi-dimensional. At one level, it explores the boundaries of anthropological practice in relation to the researcher's subjective and objective engagement in the field, in the context of documenting the knowledge of the world. On the other hand, it explores how the individuals and collective practices are produced by the history – structuring process of the ‘individual’ and the structures (organizations and institutes). As Bourdieu mentioned, *habitus* is the product of history. For him, individual subject is nothing other than the past experiences which were a disposition in the forms of schemes of perceptions, thoughts, and action there by correcting our practices. (Bourdieu, 2007; 54). Experience of individuals is a system of structured and structuring dispositions of the object of knowledge which is constituted in practices and is always oriented towards practical functions (Bourdieu, 2007;53). Thus, by means of knowledge what we understand is the system of practices enunciated by the system and structures of the histor(ies). His articulation on *habitus* is useful to understand both the construction of the writer and the domain of writing in its historical context – which is the structuring process. In this article, I use the idea of *habitus* to understand both knowledge on literature and educational practices as structured histories which are structuring individual writers in this context.

Results and discussion

Data gathered from the evaluation reports were categorized under four main themes as they emerged. (a) Participants ability to comment on the content which were related to the main concepts of the creative writing process, (b) comments on teaching and evaluation, (c) comments on art appreciation and general comments such as offer of encouragements and notes of thanking were in them. The main purpose of the evaluation reports was to comprehend the learning experiences of the participants' and their thoughts on the six themes which the content of the entire workshop is centered around and its relevance to transform their creative persona. The data of the six sessions were analyzed together. Accordingly, out of 146 documents of 35 respondents of the session three, 76 have commented on the content while 49 commented on teaching methods and evaluation, 06 of them have commented on art appreciation while 14 of them commented on general themes such as thanking and encouragement. Out of 146 documents of 35 participants, 28 of them have commented on more than two themes. These finding suggest that majority of them were more concerned about the teaching methods while comments on the content were dropped into the second highest responding category. Proportionately, small number of participants (4/34) were able to relate the content of the session and the teaching methods.

Participants who commented specifically on content and both on content and the teaching methods, were actively involved in learning process with the intention of delivering a final product at the end of the training. Those who have commented solely on teaching methods can be categorically divided into first as participants who are purely interested in listening to lectures on literature but do not thoroughly believe in literary production or production of creative writer as a production of social process. Second category consists of people those who demonstrated their view on their inability to grasp the new concepts or ideas in relation to the creative process. For instance, when they were asked to observe an event or a recurrent activity of a person and to document it in plain language, without bringing their imaginative expressions which are the vital parts of the literary writing, majority of them were not capable enough to handle the task. In contrast to the required task, most of them produced documents loaded with imaginative expressions. This could be mainly the result of their excitement to go one step ahead to produce a piece of writing as a result of the newly gained ability to write in detail or their incapacity to comprehend the task.

Responses or comments raised during the question and answer sessions revealed that some of these participants are not keen to unlearn the preconceived idea of literary production which is vital in this program as the idea of writer is constructed upon new ideological ground mentioned above. Instead, some of their attitudes were focused more on defending their inability to comprehend and translate the idea of literary production as a practice that one must learn and engage in. This is a result of the inculcated attitudes and beliefs about literature and the act of writing which inherited from the formal and informal education. The term formal education relates to the education received from schools and

universities, while informal education relates to the knowledge received from other forms of practices such as media, literary discussions and art appreciation program etc.

As many respondents mentioned, they were unaware of the concept that skills for writing literature can be learned. Particularly, they were unaware of the conceptual precision that they learned in art appreciation lessons in the school and public art reviewing forums, and its' applicability to produce a piece of art as two different things. The latter is something that needs to be taught in creative writing classes. For example, as some respondents mentioned, even if they knew about the literary devices such as the plot, experience, narrative, character development, situation building, metaphorical and other forms of language use as fundamental aspect of literary appreciation, they were unaware about the ways in which a simple plot is expanded to a narrative through the development of characters and situations. Even though few participants had published earlier, such pieces of writings demonstrate amateur level standards. Though, it is obvious that many great writers developed their skills through self-studies, it is equally true that they were matured in writing in a context where the environment for writing is conducive. For most of them, writing has become one and only passion in their lives, which is not the case for some participants who attended the workshop.

As some respondents mentioned, they have noticed the potentials they hold to write. Moreover, the encouragement they received from the literature teacher in the school, peers, or sometimes family members encouraged them to write, which was not a practice in the cause of life. Instead, the motivation for writing has been hampered by life events such as marriage, economic hardships etc. Disruption during the early stages of their writing have not allowed them to master their writing skills.

Furthermore, trends in new technologies such as proliferation of social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp and new media culture were playing a dual role both positively and negatively. Many of the youth participants whenever in their 30s, stressed that writing small stories on those platforms supported them to be recognized among a wider audience, to share their thoughts escaping from the monopolies and gate keepers of publishing industry. Hundreds of encouraging messages they received bolstered their confidence in writing. Some of them were also able to publish a few novels following the encouragement. Unfortunately, the evaluation of such texts revealed that almost all the writings were not up to the standards of the use of literary devices effectively. Though the term 'standard' is quite problematic in sociological sense on the grounds of 'whose standards', the standards are socially and institutionally produced conventions (Zolberg,1990). We might argue that these writings were hardly a fit with the use of literary devices effectively. Further discussions with the above participants confirmed that they have not sufficiently studied to appropriate those literary devices in creative writing process either formally or informally. Participants confirmed that not only their friends were capable enough to provide critical comments on their writings, but also they are not versatile readers. More importantly,

exposure to the world of literature of these participants were minimal. The average reading of the participants was limited 1 to 3 texts over a span of three months.

Nevertheless, participants over 50 demonstrated a reasonable volume of reading of old texts, most often, the text read during their studies and continued but limited to the exposure to the recent publications. They were also exposed to the world of literature, mainly soviet and Indian literature. Further the findings demonstrated a strong generational difference between the younger and the older. Overall, these findings suggest the rate of improvement of the participants in the program is slow and their development is constrained by the two issues; the historical construction of the individual (which demonstrates the difficulties to unlearn and to comprehend) and the macro scale structuring process over the system of education and its effect on the individual. This will be interpreted below.

Understanding the creator: *Habitus*

Constraints to be unlearned and ability to impart new skills cannot be understood without understanding the historical development of its institutional and epistemological practices. To explain this, I utilize Bourdieu's (2007) idea of *habitus* constituted previously. Following Bourdieu's analysis, I use the term *habitus* as embodied history – which is internalized as a second nature and forgotten as a history (Bourdieu, 2007; 56), - by the same token in its institutional form and individual form. As Bourdieu mentioned, *habitus* is a world living in a world in greater consonance, as the disposition knowledge of history lived in both entities – the social and the individuals (Bourdieu, 2007). Accordingly, historical practices internalized in social organizations, institutions, systems, and generally work as regularities in individual practice in the world, so as the individual. An individual acts according to the norms, values, attitudes stipulated by the history of the structures. The participants in this study demonstrated their struggle to comprehend the key objectives of the sessions and their difficulties to engage in the process, first, to unlearn and second, to learn that which needs to be understood in this context. This can be understood by analyzing the structuring process of the education system, as well as art education throughout its history, and consequently produce individuals parallel to the history of the production of the total structure.

Participants of this study possess two forms of *habitus* – (a) structured and structuring process by the system of education (history) and knowledge in art and (b) culture in broader terms. One form of historical knowledge and embodiment of practices represents the continuing effects of the knowledge derived from the pre-colonial education and its appropriation by the nationalist movement to confront education which structured by the colonial government. Second, participants also demonstrated the internalization of history produced by colonial education and its continuation in the post-colonial educational system. Literary thoughts produced by the former category consist of the ideas shaped by the religious (Buddhist and Hindu) ethos and nationalist sentiments. Majority of the classical texts and poetry including Sandesha Kavaya and Work of P.B. Alwis Perera, Piyadasa Sirisena are some of the examples. The latter category of the system consists of literary thoughts akin to the

ideas derived mainly from the literature received from the West including Russia and France. Works of W.A. Silva, Martin Wickramasinghe, Siri Gunasinghe are some examples. These two forms of ideologies on literature embedded to the structuring process of education there by effecting on individuals.

The development of existing educational practice is a result of the colonial modernity (Scott, 1999). As a system of practice, the structuring process of the existing education followed three stages of historical development: pre-colonial education system, the colonial education system and the post independent educational structuring process. Rationality, scientific thinking has given its shape to the rise of modern education as a system albeit the expressions of its ritualistic aspects were inherited from the church and native cultural attitudes. Influenced by pre-colonial education practices was not much different from its European tradition except different modality of rationalization about the world. Ideologically, its roots were connected to the religious attitudes and values. Though the freedom for thinking was not restricted by the temple, accessibility to education for the mass was limited. Majority of them were excluded either because of the impoverished nature of the masses or the other forms of exclusionary cultural mechanisms such as caste, ethnicity or wealth which constrained the general mass from having access to education thereby creating a downturn in social mobility or stagnation in social positions. As a result, practice of literature was exclusively limited to the educated class as they were the only class capable of reading and writing. Capability to write and read letters were not only the embodiment of specific skills or thoughts of practice but also a specific form of restructuring process of thoughts in relation to the idea of 'beauty', 'taste' and 'rational'. In Bourdieu's sense, it engaged in restructuring the thought process of a particular class who are capable of appreciating literature, while the rest of the masses were pushing the boundaries of folk arts or people who listen the literary canon enunciated by the educated elite. Thus, saying something beautifully was considered as a specific talent which was mysterious to the general mass. In Bourdieu's sense, it should be understood as the product of education – *a habitus*.

In short, being the product of a particular class of objective regularities, the *habitus* tends to generate all the 'reasonable', 'common sense', behaviors (and only these) which are possible within the limits of these regularities, and which are likely to be positively sanctioned because they are objectively adjusted to the logic characteristics of a particular field, whose objective future they anticipate. (Bourdieu, 2007; 56)

Yet, in its historical development, versatility for literary appreciation and production has not been disclosed as embodiment of skills and techniques, that should be cultivated over the cause of education and internalized history. Instead, such skills and techniques were obscured. The above attitude on literary practice has not changed even during the proceeding phases of the educational reforms.

The structuring process of education in Sri Lanka is ruptured by the emergence of colonial and post-colonial government. During the colonial government, access to education

was relaxed, though majority of them could not benefit due to the social conditions. Structuring process of education in the period of colonization has taken two modalities, one is the school system which was operated largely by the Catholic education system and second is the system lead by the national movements in then Ceylon as a response to the Catholic education (Stirrart, 1992). While the objective of the colonial administration to prepare a rationalized subject who is capable for the smooth operation of colonial structures which propagated under the banner of civilizing its natives through religion and education, the nationalistic movements in Ceylon intended to rescue its people from the missionizing project and the project of colonization while preparing them for the nation building project which was yet to be realized. At the third level, postcolonial state opened the doors of education to the general masses ignoring the ideological barriers such as caste and ethnicity. Free education bill, introduction of central colleges and decisions taken to teach in Sinhala medium both in school and university level were major decisions which were taken to democratize the educational practice. Both at the second and third level of the structuring process of the history of education in Ceylon and Sri Lanka produced an individual – *individual habitus* - in conjunction with the educational policies and curricula – institutional *habitus*. Educational achievements tested by the ability to read, memorize and write while the space for analytical and rational skills were downplayed. Consequently, education became an instrument within the social structure to prepare its people for a labour force while it became an instrument for the individuals to gain upward social mobility to overcome their impoverished nature. The *habitus* of the individuals produced by the specific cause of the above history of the education was a subject conditioned by the ability to memorize and forget, rather than an ability to unpack and utilize. In addition, certain level of ideological forces converged to instill national sentiments in individuals. It is in this context, arts education in general and education in literature is placed.

Above vested ideological interests are reflected from its curricula, particularly from the syllabi of art and culture education integrated to the language program and in the syllabi of history studies. School system under the colonial administration were able to maintain dual aspects of educational orientation by incorporating rigorous religious education and secular education. In addition to the mathematics and science education, a portion of literary studies were embedded to the curricula. Introduction of European literature caused to establish a new literary '*taste*' which nationalist movement saw as 'vulgar'. To respond to the above ideological stance, nationalist movements deliberately attempted to produce literature which awake nationalist sentiments that opposed the European value system. As noted earlier, this ideology was disseminated through art appreciation courses. Writers were encouraged to integrate the above ideological position into their texts. In addition, it is also believed that the task of literature is to provide some useful advice to shape human lives. The literary works embedded in the textbooks were loaded with nationalist sentiments. As some respondents noted above, their 'discomfort to think beyond those objectives', must be understood within this context. It is nothing other than the *habitus* produced within certain historical conditions.

Thus, it is noticeable that multiple subjectivities were produced in the field of literature in relation to the content and the objectives of the literary work. In general, the formation of hybrid identity (Bhabha, 1994) which disavow the legacy and effect of colonial values while retaining the instrumentality and benefits of colonialism which were symbolically represented through the emergence of literary works. Also, the literary discourse derived under the objective to promote national literary tradition and Sri Lankan identity were partly influenced by the Indian literary discourse reached mainly through Sanskrit canonical texts imbued with religious ideologies. Following that, Indian critical traditions of literary appreciation were utilized to analyze the texts produced under that discourse. For instance, Bharathamuni's *Natya Sastra*, *Dwanyaloka's* ... were placed over the poetic tradition of Aristotle. Literary devices borrowed from these traditions were used as yard sticks both to evaluate and to compose literary works. Any works that does not fit within the above measurements were undermined or rejected. Moreover, writing was conceived as a 'talent' which cannot be taught. specific programs intended to produce writers remained an untouched area. As a result, the curricula of Sri Lankan literature were entailed unconscious and implicit attitudes which sought any skills related to writing and literary appreciation as a possession of supreme set of skills which can be embodied by a luck or grace coming from unknown entities. Education was a mere supplement to enhance that talent which became a part of the curricula of literary studies both in school and universities until recently. Core value of the above ideological stances which was demonstrated through art and culture education is still prevalent in present curricula. Thus, struggle to comprehend and convince needs to be understood within the framework of habitus developed at institutional and organizational level and internalized in individuals.

In the findings, it was noticed that there was a stark difference between young participants and much older generations. The study looked at the volume of the reading of the participants. Characteristically, though the number of readings of the younger generation was limited to few texts, the older generation demonstrated extensive level of exposure to literature produced in 70's and beyond. Yet, exposure to literature by the younger generations was limited. Second, in contrast to the older generation, the younger generation was influenced by social media such as Facebook. Though accessibility to new technologies could play an influential role in developing writing skills, findings suggest that such assistance is completely determined by a number of the other factors. Language plays a critical role in this context. Most of the participants are natives who use Sinhala as the main language of expression. Very few of them were able to communicate in English but it was not sufficient enough to access materials that are circulated in English. On the other hand, the limited materials such as lectures, art appreciation discussions and even the encouraging notes that come with such tags as 'beautiful' piece of work' 'very interesting writing' are not more than the reproduction of the existing ideologies about literature. In fact, findings suggest that new technologies and social media platforms do play a negative role as they reproduce the existing ideological practices and attitudes in art. It suggests that even new the technologies are playing a role of structuring old *habitus* in virtual domain hampering the motivations for writing.

Conclusion

The objective of this article was to understand the learning process and its experience of the participants in their journey towards transforming themselves to be professional writers. The article was developed based on the learning experiences of the participants who attended the series of residential workshops on creative writing which were organized by the Department of Cultural Affairs in Sri Lanka.

Based on the above methodological execution, this article highlighted that the participants of this program demonstrated their struggle to apply the concepts and techniques which were introduced during the workshop in writing sessions. As discussed above, though they possess certain level of exposure to literature, experience in writing, and desire to elevate themselves to the level of experienced professional writers, their growth has been hampered by the structural conditions resulting the construction of writing subjects by the structuring process of the history. Pre- dispositional knowledge on art and culture, particularly in writing, not only creates a lack of institutional support but also the reproduction of archaic knowledge via the existing institutional structures such as educational policies developed throughout the histories and curricula which Bourdieu mentioned as the structural – *habitus* - social and economic conditions of the participants whose consistent involvement in writing is disrupted as well as accessibility for reading has constituted the existing writing styles, practice and attitudes of the participants. Thus, this article argues that constraints for developing a professional writer is a result of the contribution of the multi-faceted factors which relate to the construction of social, economic and political history of the country deployed by the existing educational practice in a given context.

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